

EFFECT OF BN COATING ON THE STRENGTH OF A MULLITE TYPE FIBER*

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ABSTRACT

Nextel 480 is an essentially polycrystalline mullite fiber (70 wt. % Al_2O_3 + 28 wt. % SiO_2 + 2 wt. % B_2O_3). Different thicknesses BN coating were applied as coatings on this fiber. Optical, scanning electron, and transmission electron microscopy) were used to characterize the microstructure of the coatings and fibers. The effects of coating and high temperature exposure on the fiber strength were investigated using two-parameter Weibull distribution. TEM examination showed that the BN coating had a turbostratic structure, with the basal planes lying predominantly parallel to the fiber surface. Such an orientation of coating is desirable for easy crack deflection and subsequent fiber pullout in a composite. The BN coated Nextel 480 fiber showed that Weibull mean strength increased first and then decreased with increasing coating thickness. This was due to the surface flaw healing effect of the thin coating (up to 0.3 μm) while in the case of thick BN coating (1 μm), the soft nature of the coating material had a more dominant effect and resulted in a decrease of the fiber strength. High temperature exposure of Nextel 480 resulted in grain growth, which led to a strength loss.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) reinforced by ceramic fibers are being developed for a variety of high temperature applications. Some strong and tough CMCs have been reported [1, 2]. The mechanical behavior of such composites depends upon the mechanical properties of the fiber and matrix, the fiber/matrix interfacial characteristics, and the residual stresses arising from thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber and matrix [1-9]. In particular, the ultimate strength of a CMC depends on the fiber strength characteristics [5]. Theoretical analysis and experimental observations have also shown that the amount of fiber pullout, which contributes to the toughening of a CMC, is greatly affected by the mean strength and variability in strength of the fibers [8]. Fibers are likely to undergo exposure to high temperatures during processing or service. This exposure to high temperature can result in physical and/or chemical degradation. On the other hand, interface design is a key to achieving high composite toughness. Fiber coating is a commonly used approach to control the interface characteristics [1]. Fiber coating can alter the fiber strength because of high a

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residual thermal stresses [10] or fiber surface morphology [11]. Thus, it is important to evaluate the effect of high temperature exposure and fiber coating on the strength of the fibers.

BN is used as a common coating material in CMCs. Boron nitride (BN) has a better oxidation resistance than carbon [12]. However, it should be recognized that BN also oxidizes slightly in air up to 1093 °C, and the oxidation becomes significant above 1371 °C due to the vaporization of the oxide product, B₂O₃. Above 1649 °C, the degradation of BN is accelerated because of the added effect of its dissociation [13]. However, BN is stable in neutral and reducing atmospheres to 1649 °C, and under pressure of N₂ it is stable up to 2760 °C [13]. Also it does not react with most materials. Nextel 480, a mullite type fiber, has a higher room temperature strength than other oxide fiber such as Fiber FP and PRD-166 because of its finer grain size [14]. It shows, however, a loss of strength after high temperature exposure, for example, about 75% and 60% of its room temperature strength are retained after exposure to 1000 °C and 1300 °C for 4 hours, respectively [15]. The objectives of this work were to investigate the effect of fiber coating and high temperature on the fiber strength.

STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION

The strength of a brittle material is determined by statistically distributed flaws in the material. The tensile strength has been found, both theoretically and experimentally, to follow the Weibull distribution [16]. The Weibull probability density function ($p(\sigma)$) and cumulative distribution function ($P(\sigma)$) of failure at a stress σ are as follows:

$$p(\sigma) = (\alpha/\beta) (\sigma/\beta)^{\alpha-1} \exp[-(\sigma/\beta)^\alpha] \quad (1)$$

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp[-(\sigma/\beta)^\alpha] \quad (2)$$

with $\alpha > 0$ and $\beta > 0$, where α is a shape parameter—referred to as the Weibull modulus that characterizes the flaw distribution in the material [17]—and β is a scale or local parameter which signifies a characteristic strength of the distribution. For a given value of β , the breadth of the Weibull distribution decreases as α increases. In contrast, for a given value of α , the breadth decreases as β increases. The Weibull distribution function parameters can be determined via a linear regression technique. Rearranging Eq. (2), we can write

$$\ln [1 - P(\sigma)] = -(\sigma/\beta)^\alpha \quad (3)$$

$$\ln [-\ln [1 - P(\sigma)]] = \alpha [\ln(\sigma) - \ln(\beta)] \quad (4)$$

The experimental strength data can be arranged in ascending order of values and the cumulative probability $P(\sigma_i)$ can be assigned as

$$P(\sigma_i) = i / (1 + N) \quad (5)$$

where i is the rank of the failed specimen in an ascending strength tabulation and N is the total number of specimens tested after a given exposure temperature. In this method, a least squares, straight line fit can then be obtained by applying a regression analysis to a plot of $\ln[-\ln[1 - P(\sigma)]]$ and $\ln(\sigma)$ from Eq. (4). This allows α and β to be determined from the slope and intercept, respectively. Knowing α and β , the Weibull mean tensile strength $\bar{\sigma}$ and standard deviation S are given by the following expressions:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \beta \Gamma(1 + 1/\alpha) \quad (6)$$

$$S = \beta [\Gamma(1 + 2/\alpha) - \Gamma^2(1 + 1/\alpha)]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where Γ is the gamma function.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Nextel 480 is a polycrystalline mullite fiber which is manufactured by 3M Co. as a continuous yarn. The fiber shape is oval with major and minor axes of 12 and 8 μm , respectively, and the average grain size is 0.1 μm . Transmission electron microscopic (TEM) studies were performed with a Philips EM 430 microscope (LaB₆ filament, 300 kV). Thin foils of specimens for TEM observations were prepared by dimple grinding and argon ion thinning. The foils were coated with carbon films to avoid

charging effects. Tensile tests of uncoated and coated fiber, Nextel 480, were performed both in the as-received state and after thermal aging. The thermal aging treatment of the fibers simulated the temperature range of the composite processing stages, i.e., as hot-pressed state (700 °C, 2 h, air; and 1300 °C, 1 h, vacuum) and hot-pressed + heat-treated state (700 °C, 2 h, air; 1300 °C, 1 h, vacuum; and 1320 °C, 1 h, N₂). The testing was done with a gauge length of 12 mm on a paper frame. A single fiber was glued onto a paper frame and the sides of the frame were carefully cut after it was gripped in the tensile testing machine. An Instron machine with a 5 N load cell was used at a crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min. In the case of as-received fibers, more than 20 fibers were tested. In the case of thermal -aged fibers, the number of the fiber was less than 20 because the fibers became very fragile after high temperature exposure. The cross sectional area of the oval-shaped Nextel 480 fibers was approximated as a combination of a rectangle with half circles at opposing ends [11].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TEM observations of BN coating are shown in Fig. 1. A general view of the BN coating is shown in Fig. 1(a), while Fig. 1(b) shows the dark field micrograph and the corresponding CBD pattern indicating that nanocrystalline BN exists inside the turbostratic BN layer.

Fig. 1 (a) General view of the BN coating Nextel 480 fiber and (b) the dark field micrograph and the corresponding CBD pattern indicating that nanocrystalline BN exists inside the turbostratic BN layer.

indicating that nanocrystalline BN exists inside the turbostratic BN layer. The basal planes lay predominantly parallel to the fiber surface. Such orientation of coating is desirable for easy crack deflection and subsequent fiber pullout in a composite.

The results of the Weibull analysis of uncoated and coated Nextel 480 fibers are given in Table 1, and the strength distribution of the uncoated fibers and fibers coated with different BN thickness is shown in Fig. 2. In the as-received state, the 0.3 μm BN-coated fiber showed a little higher strength than the uncoated fiber while the 1 μm BN-coated fiber showed lower strength than that. The strength

Table 1: Weibull analysis of uncoated and coated Nextel 480 fiber

Fiber	α	β (GPa)	$\bar{\sigma}$ (GPa)	S(GPa)	CV(%)
Uncoated	3.8	1.618	1.63	0.484	30
0.1 μm BN	5.7	2.154	2.00	0.407	20
0.2 μm BN	4.3	2.951	2.47	0.643	26
0.3 μm BN	5.0	1.894	1.82	0.420	23
1.0 μm BN	8.5	1.296	1.27	0.179	14

CV: Coefficient of variation

Fig. 2 Weibull probability density distribution of Nextel 480 fibers in the as-received state and after coating with BN.

increase with 0.3 μm BN coatings is thought to result from the effect of the coating healing the surface flaws of the fiber as reported elsewhere [11]. It was found that the surface of a BN-coated (0.2 μm thick) Nextel 480 fiber, exhibiting a higher strength, was smoother than the uncoated fiber. However, in the case of the 1 μm BN-coated fiber, it would appear that the fiber strength was more affected by the soft nature of the coating than the surface flaw healing effect, because of the coating was so thick that its volume fraction reached 0.31. Some portion of the strength loss might also be due to more chances for chemical corrosion of the fiber during a CVD process involving a corrosive environment, because a very thick coating such as 1 μm usually requires several CVD runs to get the desired thickness. It should be noted that any thermal stress effect, which is another common

source of fiber strength change, is out of consideration in the present case since the thermal expansion mismatch of the mullite fiber and BN coating is negligible.

The strength increased continuously with increasing BN coating thickness up to 0.2 μm and then began to decrease. This indicated that the strength loss by the soft nature of the coating and/or chemical corrosion of the fiber started to counteract the surface healing effect after a thickness 0.2 μm . The healing effect was still dominant, however, at 0.3 μm , for which the volume fraction of the coating was 0.11, as indicated by the higher strength than in the uncoated case. The Weibull modulus did not change very much up to 0.3 μm thickness but showed a considerable increase at 1 μm thickness, implying that the 1 μm coating was thick enough to make the fiber strength mainly controlled by the distribution of critical flaw size of the coating itself, which is thought to have more uniform distribution because of its turbostratic nature.

The tensile strength of both uncoated and coated Nextel 480 fibers seriously decreased after high temperature exposure, see Table 2 and Fig. 3. The uncoated and 0.3 μm BN-coated fibers, showing

Table 2: Effect of temperature on Weibull analysis of uncoated and coated Nextel 480 fibers

Fiber	α	β (GPa)	$\bar{\sigma}$ (GPa)	S(GPa)	CV(%)
As-received					
Uncoated	3.8	1.617	1.63	0.484	30
0.3 μm BN	5.0	1.894	1.82	0.420	23
After exposure					
Uncoated	3.7	0.593	0.52	0.156	30
0.3 μm BN	5.2	0.435	0.42	0.092	22

CV: Coefficient of variation

Fig. 3 Effect of high temperature exposure on the Weibull probability density distribution of Nextel 480 fiber.

Fig. 4 Surface of uncoated Nextel 480 fibers showing grain growth after high temperature exposure. (a) as-received, (b) after exposure to 1300 °C, and (c) after exposure to 1320 °C.

almost the same trend in the strength decrease, retained about 30 and 20% of the strength in the as-received state for the fibers after exposure to the hot pressing temperature and heat treatment temperature, respectively. However, the 1 μm BN-coated fiber showed less strength decrease (i.e., 50 % strength retention) and thus higher strength than the fibers exposed to hot pressing temperature. We have no data for the fibers after exposure to heat treatment temperature because it was impossible to get a single fiber from a tow due to the fact that the fibers were fragile after the heat treatment and also stuck together by the thick coating.

Such strength loss after high temperature exposure is attributed to the grain growth as shown in Fig. 4, because the flaw size in a brittle material scales with the grain size [18]. It can be seen that more grain growth occurred after exposure to heat treatment temperature and caused the fiber to have a rougher surface (i.e., larger flaw size). Although Fig. 4 illustrates the grain growth only in the uncoated fibers, we can expect the same trend in the coated fibers because the growth of the mullite grains would occur irrespective the presence of the coating. However, the grain growth in the coating itself would be negligible because boron nitride require a much higher temperature than the heat treatment temperature, 1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 1320 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, for diffusion due to its covalent bonding nature.

Figure 5 shows the surface of the 1 μm BN-coated fiber after exposure to 1320 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. It can be seen that the coating still maintained its smooth surface feature, indicating little grain growth in the coating. Also, the surface roughness was much less than that of the uncoated fiber after exposure to the same temperature (Fig. 4(c)). This is why the 1 μm BN-coated fiber showed less strength loss than other fibers after high temperature exposure. However, in the case of 0.3 μm BN-coated fiber, which showed about the same strength loss as the uncoated fiber, it is thought that the coating was not thick enough to heal the large roughness induced by the grain growth in the mullite.

In regard to the Weibull modulus, the uncoated and 0.3 μm BN-coated fibers showed little change after high temperature exposure, Table 2. For other cases, we have no data because the number of tests was not sufficient for the Weibull analysis or we could not do the test at all. This is because the fibers became fragile after high temperature exposure and broke during handling prior to the tests.

CONCLUSIONS

In the as-received condition, the 0.3 μm BN-coated fiber showed a higher strength than the uncoated fiber due to a surface flaw healing effect of the coating. However, the 1 μm BN-coated fiber showed a lower strength than the uncoated fiber, indicating that the fiber strength was more affected by the soft nature of the coating than the surface flaw healing effect, since the coating was so thick that its volume fraction reached 0.31.

After high temperature exposure the strength of uncoated and coated fibers seriously decreased because of considerable grain growth of mullite. The 1 μm BN-coated fiber exhibited less strength loss than others, owing to the smooth surface of the coating as well as a coating thickness large enough to cover the large roughness induced by grain growth of mullite.

REFERENCES

1. K.K. Chawla, **Ceramic Matrix Composites**, Chapman & Hall, London, 1993.
2. B. Bender, D. Shadwell, C. Bulik, L. Incorvati and D. Lewis, III, *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, 65 (1986) 363.
3. A.G. Evans and D.B. Marshall, *Acta. Metall.*, 37 (1989) 2567.
4. B. Budiansky, J.W. Hutchinson and A.G. Evans, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, 34 (1986) 167.

Fig. 5 Surface of 1 μm BN-coated Nextel 480 fiber after exposure to 1320 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

5. K.M. Prewo, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 21 (1986) 3590.
6. K.K. Chawla, M.K. Ferber, Z.R. Xu and R.Venkatesh, *Mater. Sci. Eng, A* 162 (1993) 35.
7. J.S. Ha and K.K. Chawla, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett*, 12 (1993) 84.
8. M.D. Thouless, O. Sbaizero, L.S. Sigl and A.G. Evans, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 74 (1989) 525.
9. J. Nunes, *Comp. Tech. Rev.*, 5 (1983) 53.
10. S.N. Patankar, R. Venkatesh and K.K. Chawla, *Scripta. Met.*, 25 (1991) 361.
11. J.A. Fernando, K.K. Chawla, M.K. Ferber, and D. Coffey, *Mater. Sci. & Eng., A* 154 (1992) 103.
12. E.G. Kendal, in **Ceramics for Advanced Technologies**, ed. J.E. Hove and W.C. Riley, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1965, p. 175.
13. **Engineering Property Data on Selected Ceramics**: Vol. 1, Nitrides, Metals, and Ceramics Information Center, Battelle, Columbus, Ohio, 1976.
14. D.J. Pysher, K.C. Goretta, R.S. Hodder, Jr., and R.E. Tressler, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 72 (1989) 284.
15. D.D. Johnson, A.R. Holtz, and M.F. Grether, *Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc.*, 8 (1987) 744.
16. W. Weibull, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 18 (1951) 293.
17. A. S. De Jayatilaka and K. Trustrum, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 12 (1977) 1426.
18. W.D. Kingery, H.K. Bowen, and D.R. Uhlmann, **Introduction to Ceramics**, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1976, p. 794.